

Modelling craftspeople for cultural heritage: a case study

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Keywords:	Digital humans, 3D modeling, 3D animation, cultural heritage

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Figure 1 / Creating the look of the virtual workers according to the background references and sources

167x54mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2/ Body creation with Fuse solution

51x38mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 3 /Fully rigged female avatar with face and body control – CC3/ Reallusion solution

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Figure 4 / Cloths from existing libraries

63x33mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 5 / Cloths manual modelling

63x33mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 6 / Placing and conforming an imported 3d mesh of a dress

34x40mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 7 / Tuning the skinning to fix collision issues between the layers

46x49mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 8 /Posable functionalities to test the skinning values

33x25mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 10 / Motion editing and retargeting

100x41mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 11 / The overall workflow we adopt

135x40mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 12 / Workers DHs presenting the Mastic factory

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Figure 13 / Visual markets in the exhibition space and calibration

53x21mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 14 / Plane detection, scaling, and lighting adjustment.

60x35mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 15 / Points of interest in the exhibition space.

56x42mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 16 / DHs narrating stories in the exhibition space

103x37mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 17 / VHs narrating Mingei stories and demonstrating the relative processes

48x37mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 18 / Comparative issues: Real vs Virtual after Mocap transfer

87x49mm (220 x 220 DPI)

Modelling craftspeople for cultural heritage: a case study

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Abstract

Intangible heritage is often linked to human actions and performances. The use of Digital Humans (DHs) for its digital representation and therefore its preservation, allows reframing the way to transmit and deal with content that is difficult to visualize. To that end, the digital human becomes an important element establishing the connection between the action, the objects, the knowledge, and the environment. In this paper, we describe the development of DHs acting as practitioners and storytellers for traditional craft processes within Virtual Environments. We present the process and the tasks involved in modelling, designing, and animating DHs, detailing the underlying technological background. Animations were completely based on real humans' motion extraction while working on the corresponding craft. As a result, we present the different DHs models created for three specific heritage Crafts: Mastic cultivation, Glass blowing and Silk weaving as well as an AR application, built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum. This paper is a practical description of the steps to model and animate virtual humans. The work aims to bring a methodology for achieving DHs creation for CH applications.

Keywords: digital humans; 3D modeling; 3D animation; motion capture; heritage crafts; cultural heritage

1. Introduction

Culture and history are traditionally related to the environment, the people, the objects, the materials, and even the habits that marked different populations and eras. For many years, researchers tried to find the optimal way to examine and simulate past cultures. Today, Virtual Reality or different kinds of Realities (Augmented, Mixed) provided us with the most powerful, affordable, and effective means to achieve this goal. The reconstruction of virtual worlds, which have been very commonly used in the last years, allow visitors to interact with environments, buildings, artifacts, and even characters of previous cultures, of different historical times and places [1]. The role of DHs in such environments is essential, as they can simulate appearances, behaviors and they can interact with the environment or with the users themselves allowing them to feel as close as possible in the environment. DHs can play different roles in a cultural heritage application, based on its needs, ranging from a storyteller, a guide, a craft worker or just to be a simple decoration. In some cases, the re-

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4 creation of old cities demands the presence of
5 virtual crowds, like in the work of Maïm et al.
6 who simulated Pompeii with crowds of virtual
7 Romans[2]. Adding coherent DHs in virtual
8 cultural heritage applications allows a better
9 understanding of the use of the architectural
10 structures, such as space dimensions as well as
11 the use of objects in a virtual scene. Their use is
12 significant in two main ways: for the
13 contextualization of the different components of
14 the virtual scene, and for establishing the link
15 between the visual and the non-visual
16 environment such as 3D models of the actors,
17 3D environment, sounds, music, voices,
18 gestures, and behavioral rules. In other words,
19 the existence of DHs can make a virtual cultural
20 heritage experience more human.

21 Tan and Rahaman have noted two types of DHs
22 used, the one with the first-person control,
23 where the user can control the navigation and
24 the view and thus the DHs can provide real-time
25 interaction and feedback to the user, and the
26 guided-tour type immersions, where users can
27 passively watch a predefined scenario[3].
28 However, nowadays it is a trend to use
29 intelligent agents that can represent and
30 simulate human behavior and personalities
31 traits[1]. DHs need to be designed as realistic as
32 possible not only in terms of appearance but also
33 in terms of personality and need to be able to
34 interact both verbally and non-verbally to
35 ensure the engagement and the immersion of the
36 user. Thus, the design, choice, and integration of
37 DHs in VR cultural heritage environments is a
38 challenging and complex procedure.

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41 In this paper, we present a case study where
42 digital humans have been used for preserving
43 cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent
44 simulation of craft processes that need to be
45 preserved through time. This study is conducted
46 in the framework of a European project [4]
47 which aims at representing and making
48 accessible both tangible and intangible aspects
49 of crafts as CH [5,6]. These crafts, Mastic and
50 Glass, are mainly conveyed from family to
51 family over time and thus, the need for
52 preservation is crucial. The existence of digital
53 humans augments the motivation of users and
54 visitors for further knowledge and enhances the
55 experience by providing more substantial
56 information. The paper is structured as follows.
57 Section 1 provides an introduction and an State
58 of the Art on the use of DHs in Heritage crafts.
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In section 2, we give an overview of the
different phases that were necessary to complete
the modeling and the animation of the DH
models, as well as the specific technical
restrictions inherent to the different
visualization platforms. Section 3 describes the
different scenarios of the Glass and Mastic
crafts where the resulting DH models are
integrated. Lastly, Section 4 presents the
discussion and the future work to follow.

1.1 State of the art

Current VR technologies offer a very realistic
experience to users, allowing them to visit 3D-
reconstructed sites or to learn actively about
heritage crafts.

The implementation of DHs involves tasks of
several technological backgrounds that each
application needs to address. First, to generate a
DH the most common approach is manual
modeling [1]. There are several methods to
achieve that, either using 3D modeling software
or using a depth camera to create the skeleton
and extract a mesh. Alternate methods have
been used, like the one of Feng et al. who
generated rapidly an avatar by using auto-
rigging qualities in automatic avatar generation
pipelines[7]. However, it is important to achieve
a high level of DHs' diversity so that realism is
ensured and creating a model from scratch is not
the ideal approach [1]. Thus, it seems more
efficient to generate animated 3D avatars via the
production of a morphable human model from
3D data that can easily be scaled. Then, another
challenge is the simulation of human clothes as
clothes must have also their proper animations
to deal with the mechanics of the body and the
fabrics. One platform that answers to that is the
Fashionizer platform by Senecal et al [8]. The
next step is the ability of DHs to interact
verbally with the users to simulate properly the
human behavior. The integration of speech has
been resolved in studies with different ways of
speech recognition.

Fulfilling all these requirements for their design,
DHs have been used with different roles in
virtual cultural heritage environments. A
common VR application in cultural heritage is
the reconstruction of ancient cultural or
historical places and the representation and
presentation of heritage crafts[10]. Foni et al.
tried to simulate the church of Hagia Sophia,
located in Istanbul using DHs with the
appropriate appearance and behavior based on

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4 historical findings [9]. A bit later,
5 Papagiannakis & Thalmann integrated DHs to
6 simulate the ancient city of Pompeii via a real-
7 time mixed reality mobile application[10].
8 Vlahakis et al. used virtual athletes to
9 reconstruct the stadium in ancient Olympia, in
10 Greece[12]. They used frames where the
11 athletes actively train and compete in the
12 stadium, and they reported that this feature
13 provided the users with a better understanding
14 of the historical site. Another example is the one
15 of Bogdanovych et al. who virtually
16 reconstructed the ancient city of Uruk and was
17 completely based on the existence of DHs[13].
18 They tried to immerse the user in a virtual
19 society by presenting a summary of a family's
20 typical day at that period. DHs can also play
21 specific roles by representing specific historic
22 characters. Kennedy et al. recreated the St
23 Andrews Cathedral and used interactive virtual
24 humans as specific characters, like Bishop
25 William de Lambertton [14]. A similar example
26 is the one of Vosinakis and Avradinis who
27 simulated an ancient Greek agora, using
28 characters of specific roles and behaviors[15].
29 An interesting example of a ceremony
30 simulation is the one of Papagiannakis et al.
31 who implemented a 16th-century virtual
32 representation of the Namaz Pray of a simulated
33 Ottoman Imam[16]. The authors wanted to use
34 their character-based story to make the
35 historical site more interesting for the user. Of
36 the same concept was the work of Carrozzino et
37 al. who simulated the engraving handcraft[17].
38 Barreau et al. used DHs to explain the on-board
39 living conditions of the Le Boullogne ship of the
40 18th century using also sound effects of weather
41 and the environment and a complete naval
42 simulation[18].
43 As mentioned above, large number of DHs have
44 also been used as crowds to simulate big cities.
45 Examples of such a simulation is the past and
46 present virtual representation of George
47 Town[19] or the virtual Romans in the city of
48 Pompeii [2]. DHs have also been used as tour
49 guides or storytellers. Chittaro et al. examined
50 the usability of virtual characters as guides in
51 virtual museums applications by using an agent
52 as a companion of the users in a 3D virtual
53 environment[20]. Rodriguez-Echavarría et al.
54 used the ARP toolkit and integrated a female
55 agent as a guide in the 17th-century German
56 town Wolfenbüttel[21]. Their agent was
57 responding to users' questions and had a basic
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natural behavior by gesture animation and
natural language understanding. Studies have
also tried to compare different digital humans
acting as storytellers in different aspects of
virtual museums environments, like a historical
sculpture and they concluded that the use of
DHs can stimulate the visitors' interest and
involvement [22, 23]. In the TinajAR project,
the authors simulated ancient Spanish cellars,
called calados and they used DHs as
craftworkers to show how to create ceramic
pieces [26]. In [24] a system architecture has
been recently developed to be used in several
cultural heritage contexts as storyteller,
enabling natural interactions with the users. In
[25] an interactive realistic human avatar is
described used as a guide and a storyteller.
Except from the virtual reality application or the
guiding virtual museums, it is a trend to use
serious games for augmenting the
understanding and the learning process in
cultural heritage. Such serious games are
usually completed by the presence of DHs that
makes the experience more engaging.
Vourvopoulos et al. proposed a brain-computer
interface system where the user can navigate
non-invasively its avatar inside ancient Rome
and can interact with other DHs [27]. A similar
example is the one of De Paolis et al. but
regarding a town of the Middle Ages [28]. Jang
et al. with their game called Muru in
Wonderland approached children motivating
them to learn the history of the city
Gwangju[29]. Another serious learning-based
game is the HippocraticaCivitasGame where
users visit the thermae of San Pietro and the
Palazzo Fruscione in Salerno, and they are
asked to solve a puzzle [30]. Recently, Isa et al.
developed a serious game to preserve the
brassware of terengganu, which is becoming
extinct due to mainly lack of apprentice and
interest from the young generations [31].
The affective and emotional impact of virtual
characters in such contexts have ready been
examined, highlighting the level of engagement
and persuasiveness the former can achieve [23].
In general, it has been argued that digital
humans in such roles can stimulate the attention
and the involvement of users, also enhancing the
level of learning [22]. Museum's approach to
storytelling has been evolved and it follows the
needs and expectations of the users [33].

2. The making of the Virtual craft workers

Traditional crafts are perhaps the most tangible manifestation of intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO). The use of animated DHs is fundamental when dealing with intangible cultural heritage [13] as this type of heritage is often related to human actions, skills, and knowledge which is difficult to describe and represent utilizing texts or photos. Due to technological advancements, motion capture techniques, applied to the artisans while producing their crafts, bring a safeguarding possibility to the know-how [32] and a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge onto others [34]. Indeed, the visualization of craft processes within inhabited Virtual Environments increases the usability and educational value of craft representation [35]. The making of this virtual representation takes into consideration motivations and constraints. One part is linked to the visual communication and the user's requirement while the other is dealing with the limitations inherent to the visualization platform.

This section details the most important tasks involved in the making of and the design of DHs, reenacting the process of making a *carafe Bontemps'* style, the Mastic cultivation, and the Silk weaving. These examples are taken from the work carried out in the framework of the European research project *Mingei* [5, 6]. It describes the different tools and methods used for achieving the desired results for each craft representation.

idea generation that helped in the creation of the desired overall impression. Looking at the case of the Mastic case study, we worked closely with the heritage partner to understand the role of the practitioners and acquire the relevant material for creating DHs.

The main objective of the partner was to enrich an area of the Chios Mastic Museum which is dedicated to the old factory of the Chios Gum Mastic Growers Association, and it consists of old machines that the Association used for processing mastic until the 1980s. The role of the DHs is to show how it was to work in the old factory of the Association by adding in the exhibition the human factor and experience.

For the creation of the DH workers, the heritage partner provided a detailed description of fictional exemplary workers of the factory based on archives of oral testimonies of people who worked at the Association. The descriptions contained background information about their childhood, education, personal history, age, clothing, work experience, etc. More precisely, for the creation of the DH workers' clothing, the partner prepared a selection of photographs of workers of the Association for us to have direct visual information according to their age and working post (i.e., the mechanic wore a specific uniform whereas women workers either wore their clothes in some posts or had working dresses in other posts).

Figure 1. Creating the look of the virtual workers according to the background references and sources

2.1 Character creation

The design of the character starts with collecting the sources and references for inspiration and

This material came directly from the Association's archive which the partner holds and manages. Another visual material was also used through snapshots from a Greek film named 'The Tree We Hurt', which was filmed in Chios in 1987 by the Greek director Dimos Avdelioidis. The film depicts the local society of the mastic villages in southern Chios and served as an additional reference of how women dressed in their everyday life at that time.

These references are meant to inspire the aesthetic of what we are working on and capture the feeling we want for our DHs (Figure 1). After having gathered all the cultural and historical information and sources, the preparation of the 3D DHs with their corresponding garments and accessories has been carried out according to the specific restrictions relevant to the different VR applications that have been developed in the framework of the anonymous project.

2.2 3D modeling of the DHs

This section gives an overview of the different necessary phases for the creation and the completion of the pipeline, from modeling the DH to exporting the animated model towards the Unity 3D platform which is used in our case study. The definition of the 3D meshes and the design of the skin surfaces of the DH body models have been conducted employing a customized pipeline that uses different commercial solutions [36, 37, 38, and 39]. The latter allows automatic generation methods, coupled with manual editing and refining.

Two types of DHs have been created for our study: realistic talking avatars, which are defined as storytellers for the On-site exhibition with full body and facial animation capabilities, and low-resolution animated avatars for mobile applications.

The DHs for the mobile application are created with a combination of different 3D software. Adobe Fuse CC/Mixamo is used for creating the body character (Figure 2), the clothes, the hair, and the rigging. The generated model is then imported into Autodesk 3DS max for geometry optimization and single mesh conversion. Manual methods, by using the editable poly tools, are preferred. They allow us to keep the regularity of the topology while the automatic methods generate a mesh geometry which is not

suitable for skin deformation, nor for a regular UV texture map generation.

The DHs dedicated to conversational agents, are meant to be part of the storytelling scenario of the Mastic factory's machine area. They are composed of 8 clothed DHs, fully rigged and with facial animation (Figure 3).

Our approach utilizes a full character creation solution software for creating bodies, coupled with 3D modeling software for clothes and accessories. Such a combination has several advantages, like the fully rigged model, ready for facial blend shapes which is required in our case for the storyteller DH. Moreover, the wide range of customization points for modifying the 3D model makes the creation of many unique DH easy and different bodies can be generated easily and modified to proportions that fit the Silhouette of the desired concept. The requirement for the blend shape system concerning the facial animation was a little tricky as it had to be combined with external Mocap files in BVH format for the animation of the body. Towards this goal, the Reallusion digital human pipeline [37] fits all these requirements since it provides a motion controller for face, body, and hands and is fully compatible with the game engine for real-time applications. Once the character is created, it can be directly exported to iClone [39] for motion retargeting and editing.

Figure 2. Body creation with Fuse solution

Figure 3. Fully rigged female avatar with face and body control – CC3/ Reallusion solution

2.3 Virtual 3D garment design

The collected data, such as images and written descriptions, are used as a base for the design of the different types of clothes and accessories according to the different scenarios. The method of creating the garments depends on the complexity of the models. Some of them are created from existing cloths libraries (Figure 4) and they are transformed and adapted by editing manually the 3D mesh, while others are modeled from scratch in 3DS max by using cloth simulation tools (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Cloths from existing libraries

Figure 5. Cloths manual modelling

The obtained model is then imported into the character creator software [30] and conformed to our rigged DH (Figure 6). To avoid the body character breaking through the clothing mesh, the conforming tools allow the automatic calculation of collision by iteration which resolves most of the issues. For hard-to-fix issues, manual mesh editing ability is used (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Placing and conforming an imported 3d mesh of a dress

Figure 7. Tuning the skinning to fix collision issues between the layers

2.3 Animating the DH

2.3.1 Rigging

Since the generated models are automatically rigged either by Mixamo [36] or by CC3 [38], an additional checking is needed to make sure that the rigging is applied correctly, and the bones are well adjusted to the 3D body. Hence, after the con-forming step of the clothes and accessories, possible functionalities are used to test the skinning values and the collision

between the body and the garment or accessory (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Posable functionalities to test the skinning values

2.3.2 Animating VHs

To create the animation files that are applied to the digital humans, a Motion Capture system [40] has been used. The output BVH files have been imported into iClone [39] software via the 3DXchange [37] pipeline to be edited, refined, and then applied to the virtual characters. 3DXchange pipeline is important since it allows the conversion of the imported external files (BVH) into a Non-Standard structure compatible with the hierarchy used for the rigging, and compatible with the Unity game engine (Figure 9).

Once converted, the animation file is imported into iClone [39] and automatically loaded into the DH (Figure 10). At this step, the motion editing panel will be used to perform the motion retargeting, taking the advantage of the Human IK and the keyframing options for modifying all the body parts of the character.

Figure 9. Converting the BVH structure to the Non-Standard skeleton in 3DXchange Tool

Figure 10. Motion editing and retargeting

3. Results

Based on a creation process optimized for real-time visualization (Figure 11), different DHs were created for each of the craft case studies: Eight DHs for the Mastic craft, one for the Glass craft, and one for the Silk craft (Figure 12). More than 15 movements for each craft have been produced and adapted to the DHs. Motion capture files were used to animate the DHs, the recorded movements were segmented into sub processes actions that correspond to a specific task presented in a certain order to enable the visitors to follow and understand the production process of each craft. The digital workers are also narrating their story and their function as part of the factory's production process, offering information about the machines used for the production process.

Figure 11. The overall workflow we adopt

Figure 12. Workers DHs presenting the Mastic factory

3.1. AR storytelling experience

In the context of Mingei project, an AR application has been built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum with DHs. DHs were created following the methodology proposed in this paper. Viewing the machines through the museum's tablets, the visitors can see DHs standing next to them, ready to share their stories and explain the functionality of the respective machines. The exact DH's location is instantiated by calibrating the tablets through special markers located at predefined spots in the exhibitions as presented in (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Visual markets in the exhibition space and calibration

When operated each of the tablets except from the localization feature described above uses plane detection from the image acquired through its camera to determine the positioning of points of interest and the scaling to be applied when presenting the DH. Furthermore, adaptations are done to the lighting of the DH to be visually close to the ambient light of the scene. An example of applying these transformations to make the DH appearing in front of persons being in a room are presented in (Figure 14) Calibration occurs

only once and when completed the tablets can be transferred to any location within the exhibition and operate seamlessly.

Figure 14. Plane detection, scaling, and lighting adjustment.

Overall, four tablets have been included in the exhibition space of the museum each on targeting a different museum location. An example of points of interest appearing from within the table screen is presented in (Figure 15). In (Figure 16) a screenshot of the application running within the museum space is shown.

Figure 15. Points of interest in the exhibition space.

Figure 16. DHs narrating stories in the exhibition space

3.1.1 The virtual factory experience

The virtual factory experience occurs in a 3D representation of an old mastic factory, where visitors can discover the machines met in the chicle and mastic oil production line and

interact with VHs standing before them. Each machine carries out a specific task in the mastic chicle/oil production line. They have been reconstructed from the machines that are exhibited in the Chios Museum; the machines were thoroughly scanned using a handheld trinocular scanner. Finally, the 3D data were further processed using the Blender 3D creation and editing software [41]. Overall, seven machines were reconstructed, namely, (i) the sifting machine, (ii) the blending machine, (iii) the cutting machine, (iv) the candy machine, (v) the revolving cylinder, (vi) the printing machine, and (vii) the distillation machine. All of them are met in the Chicle production line, except the distillation machine that is used for producing mastic oil. The 3D model of the factory building was initially created in Unity and then imported in Blender for further processing (e.g., windows and doors were cut, and a High Dynamic Range (HDR) environment texture was used, to provide ambient light in the scene). We have used Unity 2020 with the High-Definition Rendering Pipeline (HDRP). We have used the same DHs as the ones in the AR application. Each DH is placed next to its respective machine and is ready to explain the functionality of the machine, explain how the process step was performed at the factory before and after the machine acquisition, and narrate stories about their personal and work lives (Figure 17).

Figure 17. VHs narrating Mingei stories and demonstrating the relative processes

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have presented a heritage craft case study where DHs have been created to be

used for preserving cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent simulation of different craft processes [4]. These craft processes have been conveyed from family to family over the years and thus their representation and preservation are important. The existence of DHs enhances this effort by providing additional information and motivation to users.

Two types of DHs were created according to the needs of the project scenario: realistic talking DHs, acting as storytellers for the exhibition sites, with full body and facial animations, and low-resolution DHs for the online version of the mobile application. The choice of the proper software used for each type of DHs was made based on the final goal and the capabilities that DHs needed to have.

Figure 18. Comparative issues: Real vs Virtual after Mocap transfer

Virtual restitution has required accurate choices for each phase of the modelling, texturing, and special attention and must be always used when the models are prepared for real-time simulations. Furthermore, reliable source data are important for a historically and scientifically correct and accurate restitution. Comparative issues are also necessary when the restitution is targeting intangible heritage such as gestures and motions (Figure 18). Such virtual heritage simulations bring a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge, becoming a fundamental aspect for the full understanding of the historical and social development of vast communities.

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Modelling craftspeople for cultural heritage: a case study

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Abstract

Intangible heritage is often linked to human actions and performances. The use of Digital Humans (DHs) for its digital representation and therefore its preservation, allows reframing the way to transmit and deal with content that is difficult to visualize. To that end, the digital human becomes an important element establishing the connection between the action, the objects, the knowledge, and the environment. In this paper, we describe the development of DHs acting as practitioners and storytellers for traditional craft processes within Virtual Environments. We present the process and the tasks involved in modelling, designing, and animating DHs, detailing the underlying technological background. Animations were completely based on real humans' motion extraction while working on the corresponding craft. As a result, we present the different DHs models created for three specific heritage Crafts: Mastic cultivation, Glass blowing and Silk weaving as well as an AR application, built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum. This paper is a practical description of the steps to model and animate virtual humans. The work aims to bring a methodology for achieving DHs creation for CH applications.

Keywords: digital humans; 3D modeling; 3D animation; motion capture; heritage crafts; cultural heritage

1. Introduction

Culture and history are traditionally related to the environment, the people, the objects, the materials, and even the habits that marked different populations and eras. For many years, researchers tried to find the optimal way to examine and simulate past cultures. Today, Virtual Reality or different kinds of Realities (Augmented, Mixed) provided us with the most powerful, affordable, and effective means to achieve this goal. The reconstruction of virtual worlds, which have been very commonly used in the last years, allow visitors to interact with environments, buildings, artifacts, and even characters of previous cultures, of different historical times and places [1]. The role of DHs in such environments is essential, as they can simulate appearances, behaviors and they can interact with the environment or with the users themselves allowing them to feel as close as possible in the environment. DHs can play different roles in a cultural heritage application, based on its needs, ranging from a storyteller, a guide, a craft worker or just to be a simple decoration. In some cases, the re-

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4 creation of old cities demands the presence of
5 virtual crowds, like in the work of Maïm et al.
6 who simulated Pompeii with crowds of virtual
7 Romans[2]. Adding coherent DHs in virtual
8 cultural heritage applications allows a better
9 understanding of the use of the architectural
10 structures, such as space dimensions as well as
11 the use of objects in a virtual scene. Their use is
12 significant in two main ways: for the
13 contextualization of the different components of
14 the virtual scene, and for establishing the link
15 between the visual and the non-visual
16 environment such as 3D models of the actors,
17 3D environment, sounds, music, voices,
18 gestures, and behavioral rules. In other words,
19 the existence of DHs can make a virtual cultural
20 heritage experience more human.

21 Tan and Rahaman have noted two types of DHs
22 used, the one with the first-person control,
23 where the user can control the navigation and
24 the view and thus the DHs can provide real-time
25 interaction and feedback to the user, and the
26 guided-tour type immersions, where users can
27 passively watch a predefined scenario[3].
28 However, nowadays it is a trend to use
29 intelligent agents that can represent and
30 simulate human behavior and personalities
31 traits[1]. DHs need to be designed as realistic as
32 possible not only in terms of appearance but also
33 in terms of personality and need to be able to
34 interact both verbally and non-verbally to
35 ensure the engagement and the immersion of the
36 user. Thus, the design, choice, and integration of
37 DHs in VR cultural heritage environments is a
38 challenging and complex procedure.

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41 In this paper, we present a case study where
42 digital humans have been used for preserving
43 cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent
44 simulation of craft processes that need to be
45 preserved through time. This study is conducted
46 in the framework of a European project [4]
47 which aims at representing and making
48 accessible both tangible and intangible aspects
49 of crafts as CH [5,6]. These crafts, Mastic and
50 Glass, are mainly conveyed from family to
51 family over time and thus, the need for
52 preservation is crucial. The existence of digital
53 humans augments the motivation of users and
54 visitors for further knowledge and enhances the
55 experience by providing more substantial
56 information. The paper is structured as follows.
57 Section 1 provides an introduction and an State
58 of the Art on the use of DHs in Heritage crafts.
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In section 2, we give an overview of the
different phases that were necessary to complete
the modeling and the animation of the DH
models, as well as the specific technical
restrictions inherent to the different
visualization platforms. Section 3 describes the
different scenarios of the Glass and Mastic
crafts where the resulting DH models are
integrated. Lastly, Section 4 presents the
discussion and the future work to follow.

1.1 State of the art

Current VR technologies offer a very realistic
experience to users, allowing them to visit 3D-
reconstructed sites or to learn actively about
heritage crafts.

The implementation of DHs involves tasks of
several technological backgrounds that each
application needs to address. First, to generate a
DH the most common approach is manual
modeling [1]. There are several methods to
achieve that, either using 3D modeling software
or using a depth camera to create the skeleton
and extract a mesh. Alternate methods have
been used, like the one of Feng et al. who
generated rapidly an avatar by using auto-
rigging qualities in automatic avatar generation
pipelines[7]. However, it is important to achieve
a high level of DHs' diversity so that realism is
ensured and creating a model from scratch is not
the ideal approach [1]. Thus, it seems more
efficient to generate animated 3D avatars via the
production of a morphable human model from
3D data that can easily be scaled. Then, another
challenge is the simulation of human clothes as
clothes must have also their proper animations
to deal with the mechanics of the body and the
fabrics. One platform that answers to that is the
Fashionizer platform by Senecal et al [8]. The
next step is the ability of DHs to interact
verbally with the users to simulate properly the
human behavior. The integration of speech has
been resolved in studies with different ways of
speech recognition.

Fulfilling all these requirements for their design,
DHs have been used with different roles in
virtual cultural heritage environments. A
common VR application in cultural heritage is
the reconstruction of ancient cultural or
historical places and the representation and
presentation of heritage crafts[10]. Foni et al.
tried to simulate the church of Hagia Sophia,
located in Istanbul using DHs with the
appropriate appearance and behavior based on

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4 historical findings [9]. A bit later,
5 Papagiannakis & Thalmann integrated DHs to
6 simulate the ancient city of Pompeii via a real-
7 time mixed reality mobile application[10].
8 Vlahakis et al. used virtual athletes to
9 reconstruct the stadium in ancient Olympia, in
10 Greece[12]. They used frames where the
11 athletes actively train and compete in the
12 stadium, and they reported that this feature
13 provided the users with a better understanding
14 of the historical site. Another example is the one
15 of Bogdanovych et al. who virtually
16 reconstructed the ancient city of Uruk and was
17 completely based on the existence of DHs[13].
18 They tried to immerse the user in a virtual
19 society by presenting a summary of a family's
20 typical day at that period. DHs can also play
21 specific roles by representing specific historic
22 characters. Kennedy et al. recreated the St
23 Andrews Cathedral and used interactive virtual
24 humans as specific characters, like Bishop
25 William de Lambertton [14]. A similar example
26 is the one of Vosinakis and Avradinis who
27 simulated an ancient Greek agora, using
28 characters of specific roles and behaviors[15].
29 An interesting example of a ceremony
30 simulation is the one of Papagiannakis et al.
31 who implemented a 16th-century virtual
32 representation of the Namaz Pray of a simulated
33 Ottoman Imam[16]. The authors wanted to use
34 their character-based story to make the
35 historical site more interesting for the user. Of
36 the same concept was the work of Carrozzino et
37 al. who simulated the engraving handcraft[17].
38 Barreau et al. used DHs to explain the on-board
39 living conditions of the Le Boullogne ship of the
40 18th century using also sound effects of weather
41 and the environment and a complete naval
42 simulation[18].
43 As mentioned above, large number of DHs have
44 also been used as crowds to simulate big cities.
45 Examples of such a simulation is the past and
46 present virtual representation of George
47 Town[19] or the virtual Romans in the city of
48 Pompeii [2]. DHs have also been used as tour
49 guides or storytellers. Chittaro et al. examined
50 the usability of virtual characters as guides in
51 virtual museums applications by using an agent
52 as a companion of the users in a 3D virtual
53 environment[20]. Rodriguez-Echavarria et al.
54 used the ARP toolkit and integrated a female
55 agent as a guide in the 17th-century German
56 town Wolfenbüttel[21]. Their agent was
57 responding to users' questions and had a basic
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natural behavior by gesture animation and
natural language understanding. Studies have
also tried to compare different digital humans
acting as storytellers in different aspects of
virtual museums environments, like a historical
sculpture and they concluded that the use of
DHs can stimulate the visitors' interest and
involvement [22, 23]. In the TinajAR project,
the authors simulated ancient Spanish cellars,
called calados and they used DHs as
craftworkers to show how to create ceramic
pieces [26]. In [24] a system architecture has
been recently developed to be used in several
cultural heritage contexts as storyteller,
enabling natural interactions with the users. In
[25] an interactive realistic human avatar is
described used as a guide and a storyteller.
Except from the virtual reality application or the
guiding virtual museums, it is a trend to use
serious games for augmenting the
understanding and the learning process in
cultural heritage. Such serious games are
usually completed by the presence of DHs that
makes the experience more engaging.
Vourvopoulos et al. proposed a brain-computer
interface system where the user can navigate
non-invasively its avatar inside ancient Rome
and can interact with other DHs [27]. A similar
example is the one of De Paolis et al. but
regarding a town of the Middle Ages [28]. Jang
et al. with their game called Muru in
Wonderland approached children motivating
them to learn the history of the city
Gwangju[29]. Another serious learning-based
game is the HippocraticaCivitasGame where
users visit the thermae of San Pietro and the
Palazzo Fruscione in Salerno, and they are
asked to solve a puzzle [30]. Recently, Isa et al.
developed a serious game to preserve the
brassware of terengganu, which is becoming
extinct due to mainly lack of apprentice and
interest from the young generations [31].
The affective and emotional impact of virtual
characters in such contexts have ready been
examined, highlighting the level of engagement
and persuasiveness the former can achieve [23].
In general, it has been argued that digital
humans in such roles can stimulate the attention
and the involvement of users, also enhancing the
level of learning [22]. Museum's approach to
storytelling has been evolved and it follows the
needs and expectations of the users [33].

2. The making of the Virtual craft workers

Traditional crafts are perhaps the most tangible manifestation of intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO). The use of animated DHs is fundamental when dealing with intangible cultural heritage [13] as this type of heritage is often related to human actions, skills, and knowledge which is difficult to describe and represent utilizing texts or photos. Due to technological advancements, motion capture techniques, applied to the artisans while producing their crafts, bring a safeguarding possibility to the know-how [32] and a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge onto others [34]. Indeed, the visualization of craft processes within inhabited Virtual Environments increases the usability and educational value of craft representation [35]. The making of this virtual representation takes into consideration motivations and constraints. One part is linked to the visual communication and the user's requirement while the other is dealing with the limitations inherent to the visualization platform.

This section details the most important tasks involved in the making of and the design of DHs, reenacting the process of making a carafe Bontemps' style, the Mastic cultivation, and the Silk weaving. These examples are taken from the work carried out in the framework of the European research project Mingei [5, 6]. It describes the different tools and methods used

for achieving the desired results for each craft representation.

2.1 Character creation

The design of the character starts with collecting the sources and references for inspiration and idea generation that helped in the creation of the desired overall impression. Looking at the case of the Mastic case study, we worked closely with the heritage partner to understand the role of the practitioners and acquire the relevant material for creating DHs.

The main objective of the partner was to enrich an area of the Chios Mastic Museum which is dedicated to the old factory of the Chios Gum Mastic Growers Association, and it consists of old machines that the Association used for processing mastic until the 1980s. The role of the DHs is to show how it was to work in the old factory of the Association by adding in the exhibition the human factor and experience.

For the creation of the DH workers, the heritage partner provided a detailed description of fictional exemplary workers of the factory based on archives of oral testimonies of people who worked at the Association. The descriptions contained background information about their childhood, education, personal history, age, clothing, work experience, etc. More precisely, for the creation of the DH workers' clothing, the partner prepared a selection of photographs of workers of the Association for us to have direct visual information according to their age and working post (i.e., the mechanic wore a specific uniform whereas women workers either wore their clothes in some posts or had working dresses in other posts).

Figure 1. Creating the look of the virtual workers according to the background references and sources

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4 This material came directly from the
5 Association's archive which the partner holds
6 and manages. Another visual material was also
7 used through snapshots from a Greek film
8 named 'The Tree We Hurt', which was filmed
9 in Chios in 1987 by the Greek director Dimos
10 Avdelioidis. The film depicts the local society of
11 the mastic villages in southern Chios and served
12 as an additional reference of how women
13 dressed in their everyday life at that time.

14 These references are meant to inspire the
15 aesthetic of what we are working on and capture
16 the feeling we want for our DHs (Figure 1).
17 After having gathered all the cultural and
18 historical information and sources, the
19 preparation of the 3D DHs with their
20 corresponding garments and accessories has
21 been carried out according to the specific re-
22 strictions relevant to the different VR
23 applications that have been developed in the
24 framework of the anonymous project.
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27 2.2 3D modeling of the DHs

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29 This section gives an overview of the different
30 necessary phases for the creation and the
31 completion of the pipeline, from modeling the
32 DH to exporting the animated model towards
33 the Unity 3D platform which is used in our case
34 study. The definition of the 3D meshes and the
35 design of the skin surfaces of the DH body
36 models have been conducted employing a
37 customized pipeline that uses different
38 commercial solutions [36, 37, 38, and 39]. The
39 latter allows automatic generation methods,
40 coupled with manual editing and refining.

41 Two types of DHs have been created for our
42 study: realistic talking avatars, which are
43 defined as storytellers for the On-site exhibition
44 with full body and facial animation capabilities,
45 and low-resolution animated avatars for mobile
46 applications.
47

48 The DHs for the mobile application are created
49 with a combination of different 3D software.
50 Adobe Fuse CC/Mixamo is used for creating the
51 body character (Figure 2), the clothes, the hair,
52 and the rigging. The generated model is then
53 imported into Autodesk 3DS max for geometry
54 optimization and single mesh conversion.
55 Manual methods, by using the editable poly
56 tools, are preferred. They allow us to keep the
57 regularity of the topology while the automatic
58 methods generate a mesh geometry which is not
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suitable for skin deformation, nor for a regular
UV texture map generation.

The DHs dedicated to conversational agents, are
meant to be part of the storytelling scenario of
the Mastic factory's machine area. They are
composed of 8 clothed DHs, fully rigged and
with facial animation (Figure 3).

Our approach utilizes a full character creation
solution software for creating bodies, coupled
with 3D modeling software for clothes and
accessories. Such a combination has several
advantages, like the fully rigged model, ready
for facial blend shapes which is required in our
case for the storyteller DH. Moreover, the wide
range of customization points for modifying the
3D model makes the creation of many unique
DH easy and different bodies can be generated
easily and modified to proportions that fit the
Silhouette of the desired concept. The
requirement for the blend shape system
concerning the facial animation was a little
tricky as it had to be combined with external
Mocap files in BVH format for the animation of
the body. Towards this goal, the Reallusion
digital human pipeline [37] fits all these
requirements since it provides a motion
controller for face, body, and hands and is fully
compatible with the game engine for real-time
applications. Once the character is created, it
can be directly exported to iClone [39] for
motion retargeting and editing.

Figure 2. Body creation with Fuse solution

Figure 3. Fully rigged female avatar with face and body control – CC3/ Reallusion solution

2.3 Virtual 3D garment design

The collected data, such as images and written descriptions, are used as a base for the design of the different types of clothes and accessories according to the different scenarios. The method of creating the garments depends on the complexity of the models. Some of them are created from existing cloths libraries (Figure 4) and they are transformed and adapted by editing manually the 3D mesh, while others are modeled from scratch in 3DS max by using cloth simulation tools (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Cloths from existing libraries

Figure 5. Cloths manual modelling

The obtained model is then imported into the character creator software [30] and conformed to our rigged DH (Figure 6). To avoid the body character breaking through the clothing mesh, the conforming tools allow the automatic calculation of collision by iteration which resolves most of the issues. For hard-to-fix issues, manual mesh editing ability is used (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Placing and conforming an imported 3d mesh of a dress

Figure 7. Tuning the skinning to fix collision issues between the layers

2.3 Animating the DH

2.3.1 Rigging

Since the generated models are automatically rigged either by Mixamo [36] or by CC3 [38],

an additional checking is needed to make sure that the rigging is applied correctly, and the bones are well adjusted to the 3D body. Hence, after the con-forming step of the clothes and accessories, possible functionalities are used to test the skinning values and the collision between the body and the garment or accessory (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Possible functionalities to test the skinning values

2.3.2 Animating VHs

To create the animation files that are applied to the digital humans, a Motion Capture system [40] has been used. The output BVH files have been imported into iClone [39] software via the 3DXchange [37] pipeline to be edited, refined, and then applied to the virtual characters. 3DXchange pipeline is important since it allows the conversion of the imported external files (BVH) into a Non-Standard structure compatible with the hierarchy used for the rigging, and compatible with the Unity game engine (Figure 9).

Once converted, the animation file is imported into iClone [39] and automatically loaded into the DH (Figure 10). At this step, the motion editing panel will be used to perform the motion retargeting, taking the advantage of the Human IK and the keyframing options for modifying all the body parts of the character.

Figure 9. Converting the BVH structure to the Non-Standard skeleton in 3DXchange Tool

Figure 10. Motion editing and retargeting

3. Results

Based on a creation process optimized for real-time visualization (Figure 11), different DHs were created for each of the craft case studies: Eight DHs for the Mastic craft, one for the Glass craft, and one for the Silk craft (Figure 12). More than 15 movements for each craft have been produced and adapted to the DHs. Motion capture files were used to animate the DHs, the recorded movements were segmented into sub processes actions that correspond to a specific task presented in a certain order to enable the visitors to follow and understand the production process of each craft. The digital workers are also narrating their story and their function as part of the factory's production process, offering information about the machines used for the production process.

Figure 11. The overall workflow we adopt

Figure 12. Workers DHs presenting the Mastic factory

3.1. AR storytelling experience

In the context of Mingei project, an AR application has been built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum with DHs. DHs were created following the methodology proposed in this paper. Viewing the machines through the museum's tablets, the visitors can see DHs standing next to them, ready to share their stories and explain the functionality of the respective machines. The exact DH's location is instantiating by calibrating the tablets through special markers located at predefined spots in the exhibitions as presented in (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Visual markets in the exhibition space and calibration

When operated each of the tablets except from the localization feature described above uses plane detection from the image acquired through its camera to determine the positioning of points of interest and the scaling to be applied when presenting the DH. Furthermore,

adaptations are done to the lighting of the DH to be visually close to the ambient light of the scene. An example of applying these transformations to make the DH appearing in front of persons being in a room are presented in (Figure 14) Calibration occurs only once and when completed the tablets can be transferred to any location within the exhibition and operate seamlessly.

Figure 14. Plane detection, scaling, and lighting adjustment.

Overall, four tablets have been included in the exhibition space of the museum each on targeting a different museum location. An example of points of interest appearing from within the tablet screen is presented in (Figure 15). In (Figure 16) a screenshot of the application running within the museum space is shown.

Figure 15. Points of interest in the exhibition space.

Figure 16. DHs narrating stories in the exhibition space

3.1.1 The virtual factory experience

The virtual factory experience occurs in a 3D representation of an old mastic factory, where visitors can discover the machines met in the chicle and mastic oil production line and interact with VHS standing before them. Each machine carries out a specific task in the mastic chicle/oil production line. They have been reconstructed from the machines that are exhibited in the Chios Museum; the machines were thoroughly scanned using a handheld trinocular scanner. Finally, the 3D data were further processed using the Blender 3D creation and editing software [41]. Overall, seven machines were reconstructed, namely, (i) the sifting machine, (ii) the blending machine, (iii) the cutting machine, (iv) the candy machine, (v) the revolving cylinder, (vi) the printing machine, and (vii) the distillation machine. All of them are met in the Chicle production line, except the distillation machine that is used for producing mastic oil. The 3D model of the factory building was initially created in Unity and then imported in Blender for further processing (e.g., windows and doors were cut, and a High Dynamic Range (HDR) environment texture was used, to provide ambient light in the scene). We have used Unity 2020 with the High-Definition Rendering Pipeline (HDRP). We have used the same DHs as the ones in the AR application. Each DH is placed next to its respective machine and is ready to explain the functionality of the machine, explain how the process step was performed at the factory before and after the machine acquisition, and narrate stories about their personal and work lives (Figure 17).

Figure 17. VHS narrating Mingei stories and demonstrating the relative processes

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have presented a heritage craft case study where DHs have been created to be used for preserving cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent simulation of different craft processes [4]. These craft processes have been conveyed from family to family over the years and thus their representation and preservation are important. The existence of DHs enhances this effort by providing additional information and motivation to users.

Two types of DHs were created according to the needs of the project scenario: realistic talking DHs, acting as storytellers for the exhibition sites, with full body and facial animations, and low-resolution DHs for the online version of the mobile application. The choice of the proper software used for each type of DHs was made based on the final goal and the capabilities that DHs needed to have.

Figure 18. Comparative issues: Real vs Virtual after Mocap transfer

Virtual restitution has required accurate choices for each phase of the modelling, texturing, and special attention and must be always used when the models are prepared for real-time simulations. Furthermore, reliable source data are important for a historically and scientifically correct and accurate restitution. Comparative issues are also necessary when the restitution is targeting intangible heritage such as gestures and motions (Figure 18). Such virtual heritage simulations bring a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge, becoming a fundamental aspect for the full understanding of the historical and social development of vast communities.

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Modelling craftspeople for cultural heritage: a case study

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Abstract

Intangible heritage is often linked to human actions and performances. The use of Digital Humans (DHs) for its digital representation and therefore its preservation, allows reframing the way to transmit and deal with content that is difficult to visualize. To that end, the digital human becomes an important element establishing the connection between the action, the objects, the knowledge, and the environment. In this paper, we describe the development of DHs acting as practitioners and storytellers for traditional craft processes within Virtual Environments. We present the process and the tasks involved in modelling, designing, and animating DHs, detailing the underlying technological background. Animations were completely based on real humans' motion extraction while working on the corresponding craft. As a result, we present the different DHs models created for three specific heritage Crafts: Mastic cultivation, Glass blowing and Silk weaving as well as an AR application, built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum. This paper is a practical description of the steps to model and animate virtual humans. The work aims to bring a methodology for achieving DHs creation for CH applications.

Keywords: digital humans; 3D modeling; 3D animation; motion capture; heritage crafts; cultural heritage

1. Introduction

Culture and history are traditionally related to the environment, the people, the objects, the materials, and even the habits that marked different populations and eras. For many years, researchers tried to find the optimal way to examine and simulate past cultures. Today, Virtual Reality or different kinds of Realities (Augmented, Mixed) provided us with the most powerful, affordable, and effective means to achieve this goal. The reconstruction of virtual worlds, which have been very commonly used in the last years, allow visitors to interact with environments, buildings, artifacts, and even characters of previous cultures, of different historical times and places [1]. The role of DHs in such environments is essential, as they can simulate appearances, behaviors and they can interact with the environment or with the users themselves allowing them to feel as close as possible in the environment.

DHs can play different roles in a cultural heritage application, based on its needs, ranging from a storyteller, a guide, a craft worker or just to be a simple decoration. In some cases, the re-

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4 creation of old cities demands the presence of
5 virtual crowds, like in the work of Maïm et al.
6 who simulated Pompeii with crowds of virtual
7 Romans[2]. Adding coherent DHs in virtual
8 cultural heritage applications allows a better
9 understanding of the use of the architectural
10 structures, such as space dimensions as well as
11 the use of objects in a virtual scene. Their use is
12 significant in two main ways: for the
13 contextualization of the different components of
14 the virtual scene, and for establishing the link
15 between the visual and the non-visual
16 environment such as 3D models of the actors,
17 3D environment, sounds, music, voices,
18 gestures, and behavioral rules. In other words,
19 the existence of DHs can make a virtual cultural
20 heritage experience more human.

21 Tan and Rahaman have noted two types of DHs
22 used, the one with the first-person control,
23 where the user can control the navigation and
24 the view and thus the DHs can provide real-time
25 interaction and feedback to the user, and the
26 guided-tour type immersions, where users can
27 passively watch a predefined scenario[3].
28 However, nowadays it is a trend to use
29 intelligent agents that can represent and
30 simulate human behavior and personalities
31 traits[1]. DHs need to be designed as realistic as
32 possible not only in terms of appearance but also
33 in terms of personality and need to be able to
34 interact both verbally and non-verbally to
35 ensure the engagement and the immersion of the
36 user. Thus, the design, choice, and integration of
37 DHs in VR cultural heritage environments is a
38 challenging and complex procedure.

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41 In this paper, we present a case study where
42 digital humans have been used for preserving
43 cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent
44 simulation of craft processes that need to be
45 preserved through time. This study is conducted
46 in the framework of a European project [4]
47 which aims at representing and making
48 accessible both tangible and intangible aspects
49 of crafts as CH [5,6]. These crafts, Mastic and
50 Glass, are mainly conveyed from family to
51 family over time and thus, the need for
52 preservation is crucial. The existence of digital
53 humans augments the motivation of users and
54 visitors for further knowledge and enhances the
55 experience by providing more substantial
56 information. The paper is structured as follows.
57 Section 1 provides an introduction and an State
58 of the Art on the use of DHs in Heritage crafts.
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In section 2, we give an overview of the
different phases that were necessary to complete
the modeling and the animation of the DH
models, as well as the specific technical
restrictions inherent to the different
visualization platforms. Section 3 describes the
different scenarios of the Glass and Mastic
crafts where the resulting DH models are
integrated. Lastly, Section 4 presents the
discussion and the future work to follow.

1.1 State of the art

Current VR technologies offer a very realistic
experience to users, allowing them to visit 3D-
reconstructed sites or to learn actively about
heritage crafts.

The implementation of DHs involves tasks of
several technological backgrounds that each
application needs to address. First, to generate a
DH the most common approach is manual
modeling [1]. There are several methods to
achieve that, either using 3D modeling software
or using a depth camera to create the skeleton
and extract a mesh. Alternate methods have
been used, like the one of Feng et al. who
generated rapidly an avatar by using auto-
rigging qualities in automatic avatar generation
pipelines[7]. However, it is important to achieve
a high level of DHs' diversity so that realism is
ensured and creating a model from scratch is not
the ideal approach [1]. Thus, it seems more
efficient to generate animated 3D avatars via the
production of a morphable human model from
3D data that can easily be scaled. Then, another
challenge is the simulation of human clothes as
clothes must have also their proper animations
to deal with the mechanics of the body and the
fabrics. One platform that answers to that is the
Fashionizer platform by Senecal et al [8]. The
next step is the ability of DHs to interact
verbally with the users to simulate properly the
human behavior. The integration of speech has
been resolved in studies with different ways of
speech recognition.

Fulfilling all these requirements for their design,
DHs have been used with different roles in
virtual cultural heritage environments. A
common VR application in cultural heritage is
the reconstruction of ancient cultural or
historical places and the representation and
presentation of heritage crafts[10]. Foni et al.
tried to simulate the church of Hagia Sophia,
located in Istanbul using DHs with the
appropriate appearance and behavior based on

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4 historical findings [9]. A bit later,
5 Papagiannakis & Thalmann integrated DHs to
6 simulate the ancient city of Pompeii via a real-
7 time mixed reality mobile application[10].
8 Vlahakis et al. used virtual athletes to
9 reconstruct the stadium in ancient Olympia, in
10 Greece[12]. They used frames where the
11 athletes actively train and compete in the
12 stadium, and they reported that this feature
13 provided the users with a better understanding
14 of the historical site. Another example is the one
15 of Bogdanovych et al. who virtually
16 reconstructed the ancient city of Uruk and was
17 completely based on the existence of DHs[13].
18 They tried to immerse the user in a virtual
19 society by presenting a summary of a family's
20 typical day at that period. DHs can also play
21 specific roles by representing specific historic
22 characters. Kennedy et al. recreated the St
23 Andrews Cathedral and used interactive virtual
24 humans as specific characters, like Bishop
25 William de Lambertton [14]. A similar example
26 is the one of Vosinakis and Avradinis who
27 simulated an ancient Greek agora, using
28 characters of specific roles and behaviors[15].
29 An interesting example of a ceremony
30 simulation is the one of Papagiannakis et al.
31 who implemented a 16th-century virtual
32 representation of the Namaz Pray of a simulated
33 Ottoman Imam[16]. The authors wanted to use
34 their character-based story to make the
35 historical site more interesting for the user. Of
36 the same concept was the work of Carrozzino et
37 al. who simulated the engraving handcraft[17].
38 Barreau et al. used DHs to explain the on-board
39 living conditions of the Le Boullogne ship of the
40 18th century using also sound effects of weather
41 and the environment and a complete naval
42 simulation[18].
43 As mentioned above, large number of DHs have
44 also been used as crowds to simulate big cities.
45 Examples of such a simulation is the past and
46 present virtual representation of George
47 Town[19] or the virtual Romans in the city of
48 Pompeii [2]. DHs have also been used as tour
49 guides or storytellers. Chittaro et al. examined
50 the usability of virtual characters as guides in
51 virtual museums applications by using an agent
52 as a companion of the users in a 3D virtual
53 environment[20]. Rodriguez-Echavarria et al.
54 used the ARP toolkit and integrated a female
55 agent as a guide in the 17th-century German
56 town Wolfenbüttel[21]. Their agent was
57 responding to users' questions and had a basic
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natural behavior by gesture animation and
natural language understanding. Studies have
also tried to compare different digital humans
acting as storytellers in different aspects of
virtual museums environments, like a historical
sculpture and they concluded that the use of
DHs can stimulate the visitors' interest and
involvement [22, 23]. In the TinajAR project,
the authors simulated ancient Spanish cellars,
called calados and they used DHs as
craftworkers to show how to create ceramic
pieces [26]. In [24] a system architecture has
been recently developed to be used in several
cultural heritage contexts as storyteller,
enabling natural interactions with the users. In
[25] an interactive realistic human avatar is
described used as a guide and a storyteller.
Except from the virtual reality application or the
guiding virtual museums, it is a trend to use
serious games for augmenting the
understanding and the learning process in
cultural heritage. Such serious games are
usually completed by the presence of DHs that
makes the experience more engaging.
Vourvopoulos et al. proposed a brain-computer
interface system where the user can navigate
non-invasively its avatar inside ancient Rome
and can interact with other DHs [27]. A similar
example is the one of De Paolis et al. but
regarding a town of the Middle Ages [28]. Jang
et al. with their game called Muru in
Wonderland approached children motivating
them to learn the history of the city
Gwangju[29]. Another serious learning-based
game is the HippocraticaCivitasGame where
users visit the thermae of San Pietro and the
Palazzo Fruscione in Salerno, and they are
asked to solve a puzzle [30]. Recently, Isa et al.
developed a serious game to preserve the
brassware of terengganu, which is becoming
extinct due to mainly lack of apprentice and
interest from the young generations [31].
The affective and emotional impact of virtual
characters in such contexts have ready been
examined, highlighting the level of engagement
and persuasiveness the former can achieve [23].
In general, it has been argued that digital
humans in such roles can stimulate the attention
and the involvement of users, also enhancing the
level of learning [22]. Museum's approach to
storytelling has been evolved and it follows the
needs and expectations of the users [33].

2. The making of the Virtual craft workers

Traditional crafts are perhaps the most tangible manifestation of intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO). The use of animated DHs is fundamental when dealing with intangible cultural heritage [13] as this type of heritage is often related to human actions, skills, and knowledge which is difficult to describe and represent utilizing texts or photos. Due to technological advancements, motion capture techniques, applied to the artisans while producing their crafts, bring a safeguarding possibility to the know-how [32] and a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge onto others [34]. Indeed, the visualization of craft processes within inhabited Virtual Environments increases the usability and educational value of craft representation [35]. The making of this virtual representation takes into consideration motivations and constraints. One part is linked to the visual communication and the user's requirement while the other is dealing with the limitations inherent to the visualization platform.

This section details the most important tasks involved in the making of and the design of DHs, reenacting the process of making a *carafe Bontemps'* style, the Mastic cultivation, and the Silk weaving. These examples are taken from the work carried out in the framework of the European research project *Mingei* [5, 6]. It describes the different tools and methods used for achieving the desired results for each craft representation.

2.1 Character creation

Figure 1. Creating the look of the virtual workers according to the background references and sources

The design of the character starts with collecting the sources and references for inspiration and

idea generation that helped in the creation of the desired overall impression. Looking at the case of the Mastic case study, we worked closely with the heritage partner to understand the role of the practitioners and acquire the relevant material for creating DHs.

The main objective of the partner was to enrich an area of the Chios Mastic Museum which is dedicated to the old factory of the Chios Gum Mastic Growers Association, and it consists of old machines that the Association used for processing mastic until the 1980s. The role of the DHs is to show how it was to work in the old factory of the Association by adding in the exhibition the human factor and experience.

For the creation of the DH workers, the heritage partner provided a detailed description of fictional exemplary workers of the factory based on archives of oral testimonies of people who worked at the Association. The descriptions contained background information about their childhood, education, personal history, age, clothing, work experience, etc. More precisely, for the creation of the DH workers' clothing, the partner prepared a selection of photographs of workers of the Association for us to have direct visual information according to their age and working post (i.e., the mechanic wore a specific uniform whereas women workers either wore their clothes in some posts or had working dresses in other posts).

This material came directly from the Association's archive which the partner holds and manages. Another visual material was also used through snapshots from a Greek film named 'The Tree We Hurt', which was filmed in Chios in 1987 by the Greek director Dimos Avdelioidis. The film depicts the local society of the mastic villages in southern Chios and served as an additional reference of how women dressed in their everyday life at that time.

These references are meant to inspire the aesthetic of what we are working on and capture the feeling we want for our DHs (Figure 1). After having gathered all the cultural and historical information and sources, the preparation of the 3D DHs with their corresponding garments and accessories has been carried out according to the specific restrictions relevant to the different VR applications that have been developed in the framework of the anonymous project.

2.2 3D modeling of the DHs

This section gives an overview of the different necessary phases for the creation and the completion of the pipeline, from modeling the DH to exporting the animated model towards the Unity 3D platform which is used in our case study. The definition of the 3D meshes and the design of the skin surfaces of the DH body models have been conducted employing a customized pipeline that uses different commercial solutions [36, 37, 38, and 39]. The latter allows automatic generation methods, coupled with manual editing and refining.

Two types of DHs have been created for our study: realistic talking avatars, which are defined as storytellers for the On-site exhibition with full body and facial animation capabilities, and low-resolution animated avatars for mobile applications.

The DHs for the mobile application are created with a combination of different 3D software. Adobe Fuse CC/Mixamo is used for creating the body character (Figure 2), the clothes, the hair, and the rigging. The generated model is then imported into Autodesk 3DS max for geometry optimization and single mesh conversion. Manual methods, by using the editable poly tools, are preferred. They allow us to keep the regularity of the topology while the automatic methods generate a mesh geometry which is not

suitable for skin deformation, nor for a regular UV texture map generation.

The DHs dedicated to conversational agents, are meant to be part of the storytelling scenario of the Mastic factory's machine area. They are composed of 8 clothed DHs, fully rigged and with facial animation (Figure 3).

Our approach utilizes a full character creation solution software for creating bodies, coupled with 3D modeling software for clothes and accessories. Such a combination has several advantages, like the fully rigged model, ready for facial blend shapes which is required in our case for the storyteller DH. Moreover, the wide range of customization points for modifying the 3D model makes the creation of many unique DH easy and different bodies can be generated easily and modified to proportions that fit the Silhouette of the desired concept. The requirement for the blend shape system concerning the facial animation was a little tricky as it had to be combined with external Mocap files in BVH format for the animation of the body. Towards this goal, the Reallusion digital human pipeline [37] fits all these requirements since it provides a motion controller for face, body, and hands and is fully compatible with the game engine for real-time applications. Once the character is created, it can be directly exported to iClone [39] for motion retargeting and editing.

Figure 2. Body creation with Fuse solution

Figure 3. Fully rigged female avatar with face and body control – CC3/ Reallusion solution

2.3 Virtual 3D garment design

The collected data, such as images and written descriptions, are used as a base for the design of the different types of clothes and accessories according to the different scenarios. The method of creating the garments depends on the complexity of the models. Some of them are created from existing cloths libraries (Figure 4) and they are transformed and adapted by editing manually the 3D mesh, while others are modeled from scratch in 3DS max by using cloth simulation tools (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Cloths from existing libraries

Figure 5. Cloths manual modelling

The obtained model is then imported into the character creator software [30] and conformed to our rigged DH (Figure 6). To avoid the body character breaking through the clothing mesh, the conforming tools allow the automatic calculation of collision by iteration which resolves most of the issues. For hard-to-fix issues, manual mesh editing ability is used (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Placing and conforming an imported 3D mesh of a dress

Figure 7. Tuning the skinning to fix collision issues between the layers

2.3 Animating the DH

2.3.1 Rigging

Since the generated models are automatically rigged either by Mixamo [36] or by CC3 [38], an additional checking is needed to make sure that the rigging is applied correctly, and the bones are well adjusted to the 3D body. Hence, after the con-forming step of the clothes and accessories, possible functionalities are used to test the skinning values and the collision

between the body and the garment or accessory (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Posable functionalities to test the skinning values

2.3.2 Animating VHs

To create the animation files that are applied to the digital humans, a Motion Capture system [40] has been used. The output BVH files have been imported into iClone [39] software via the 3DXchange [37] pipeline to be edited, refined, and then applied to the virtual characters. 3DXchange pipeline is important since it allows the conversion of the imported external files (BVH) into a Non-Standard structure compatible with the hierarchy used for the rigging, and compatible with the Unity game engine (Figure 9).

Once converted, the animation file is imported into iClone [39] and automatically loaded into the DH (Figure 10). At this step, the motion editing panel will be used to perform the motion retargeting, taking the advantage of the Human IK and the keyframing options for modifying all the body parts of the character.

Figure 9. Converting the BVH structure to the Non-Standard skeleton in 3DXchange Tool

Figure 10. Motion editing and retargeting

3. Results

Based on a creation process optimized for real-time visualization (Figure 11), different DHs were created for each of the craft case studies: Eight DHs for the Mastic craft, one for the Glass craft, and one for the Silk craft (Figure 12). More than 15 movements for each craft have been produced and adapted to the DHs. Motion capture files were used to animate the DHs, the recorded movements were segmented into sub processes actions that correspond to a specific task presented in a certain order to enable the visitors to follow and understand the production process of each craft. The digital workers are also narrating their story and their function as part of the factory's production process, offering information about the machines used for the production process.

Figure 11. The overall workflow we adopt

Figure 12. Workers DHs presenting the Mastic factory

3.1. AR storytelling experience

In the context of Mingei project, an AR application has been built to augment exhibits of the Chios Mastic Museum with DHs. DHs were created following the methodology proposed in this paper. Viewing the machines through the museum's tablets, the visitors can see DHs standing next to them, ready to share their stories and explain the functionality of the respective machines. The exact DH's location is instantiating by calibrating the tablets through special markers located at predefined spots in the exhibitions as presented in (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Visual markets in the exhibition space and calibration

When operated each of the tablets except from the localization feature described above uses plane detection from the image acquired through its camera to determine the positioning of points of interest and the scaling to be applied when presenting the DH. Furthermore, adaptations are done to the lighting of the DH to be visually close to the ambient light of the scene. An example of applying these transformations to make the DH appearing in front of persons being in a room are presented in (Figure 14) Calibration occurs

only once and when completed the tablets can be transferred to any location within the exhibition and operate seamlessly.

Figure 14. Plane detection, scaling, and lighting adjustment.

Overall, four tablets have been included in the exhibition space of the museum each on targeting a different museum location. An example of points of interest appearing from within the table screen is presented in (Figure 15). In (Figure 16) a screenshot of the application running within the museum space is shown.

Figure 15. Points of interest in the exhibition space.

Figure 16. DHs narrating stories in the exhibition space

3.1.1 The virtual factory experience

The virtual factory experience occurs in a 3D representation of an old mastic factory, where visitors can discover the machines met in the chicle and mastic oil production line and

interact with VHs standing before them. Each machine carries out a specific task in the mastic chicle/oil production line. They have been reconstructed from the machines that are exhibited in the Chios Museum; the machines were thoroughly scanned using a handheld trinocular scanner. Finally, the 3D data were further processed using the Blender 3D creation and editing software [41]. Overall, seven machines were reconstructed, namely, (i) the sifting machine, (ii) the blending machine, (iii) the cutting machine, (iv) the candy machine, (v) the revolving cylinder, (vi) the printing machine, and (vii) the distillation machine. All of them are met in the Chicle production line, except the distillation machine that is used for producing mastic oil. The 3D model of the factory building was initially created in Unity and then imported in Blender for further processing (e.g., windows and doors were cut, and a High Dynamic Range (HDR) environment texture was used, to provide ambient light in the scene). We have used Unity 2020 with the High-Definition Rendering Pipeline (HDRP). We have used the same DHs as the ones in the AR application. Each DH is placed next to its respective machine and is ready to explain the functionality of the machine, explain how the process step was performed at the factory before and after the machine acquisition, and narrate stories about their personal and work lives (Figure 17).

Figure 17. VHs narrating Mingei stories and demonstrating the relative processes

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have presented a heritage craft case study where DHs have been created to be

used for preserving cultural knowledge and for giving a consistent simulation of different craft processes [4]. These craft processes have been conveyed from family to family over the years and thus their representation and preservation are important. The existence of DHs enhances this effort by providing additional information and motivation to users.

Two types of DHs were created according to the needs of the project scenario: realistic talking DHs, acting as storytellers for the exhibition sites, with full body and facial animations, and low-resolution DHs for the online version of the mobile application. The choice of the proper software used for each type of DHs was made based on the final goal and the capabilities that DHs needed to have.

Figure 18. Comparative issues: Real vs Virtual after Mocap transfer

Virtual restitution has required accurate choices for each phase of the modelling, texturing, and special attention and must be always used when the models are prepared for real-time simulations. Furthermore, reliable source data are important for a historically and scientifically correct and accurate restitution. Comparative issues are also necessary when the restitution is targeting intangible heritage such as gestures and motions (Figure 18). Such virtual heritage simulations bring a new dimension in communicating skills and knowledge, becoming a fundamental aspect for the full understanding of the historical and social development of vast communities.

5. Acknowledgements

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Response to reviewer Comments

We thank the reviewers for their encouraging and constructive comments. All the changes we have made are also highlighted in the manuscript.

Reviewer: 1		
No	Comment	Response
1	The modelling craftspeople is significant for preserving cultural heritage. The manuscript is well-drafted and organized in general. However, there are also some problems in the paper that need to be improved and corrected.	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments
2	In the sentence "We do that through a case study in the context of ...", what does the word "that" refer to?	➤ we have rephrased as follows: This study is conducted in the framework of Mingei European project... [4]
3	"Digital Humans (DHs)" appears both in the abstract and the introduction, which is redundant.	➤ "Digital Humans (DHs)" replaced by DHs in the introduction
4	There is a reference error in the paragraph before section 1.1.	➤ References have been added
5	The title of section 2.1, namely "Character design", is a little confusing and should be clear.	➤ "Character design" replaced par "Character creation"
6	Please improve the figure quality of the manuscript, which are a little vague and the texts in the figures are hard to be recognized.	➤ Figure 11, 13 and 19 have been improved
7	The writing of some contents in the manuscript is a little strange. For example, the typos in the third paragraph of section 2.2, and the logic of the paragraph is unclear.	➤ Section 2.2: the paragraph has been reworded and the structure revised
	Originality SCORE: 3 (fair) 3 References SCORE: 3 (fair)	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments

Reviewer: 2		
No	Comment	Response
1	An interesting paper describing the process of creating digital humans and their animations in connection with the real motion of people in specific heritage crafts. Even though this process is not groundbreaking, it is clearly analyzed and explained, while at the same time exploring its possibilities and limitations.	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments
2	Originality SCORE:4(good) TEXT: The paper gives insight and useful information in the process of creating and optimizing digital humans for specific applications using commercial software.	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments
3	References SCORE: 5(excellent) TEXT: Excellent number and quality of references found on page 2 "Error! Reference source not found.", please fix	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments ➤ Error Reference has been fixed
4	Visual Results SCORE:5(excellent) TEXT: This paper is packed with visual references to the author's work that provide additional value to the paper's content.	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments
5	Style and Language SCORE: 5 (excellent) TEXT: I have really enjoyed the style of writing used by the author and easily read the paper in detail without any ambiguous parts.	The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments
6	fix the following minor mistakes: in 3.1 -> "DH in order to be visually close to the"	➤ Mistake fixed

Reviewer: 3		
No	Comment	Response
1	<p>The paper presents a case study for modeling and animation of digital humans for cultural heritage. The process of modeling of 3D models, animating them, and building an AR application containing interactive characters is described. Three specific heritage crafts are selected as the pilots: mastic cultivation, glass blowing and silk weaving.</p> <p>The paper is easy to read, and the tools used in the process are described in sufficient details. However, the paper is only a practical description of the steps, which are well known in the virtual human modeling and animation field.</p>	<p>The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments.</p> <p>➤ We have stated at the end of the abstract that: This paper is a practical description of the steps to model and animate virtual humans. The work aims to bring a methodology for achieving DHs creation for CH applications.</p>
2	<p>References SCORE: 4 (good) TEXT: All relevant papers are cited.</p>	
3	<p>Visual Results SCORE: 3(fair) TEXT: The paper could include a supplementary video demonstrating the application, especially in the museum as experienced by the visitors.</p>	<p>➤ The website of the project which is referenced in [4] contains all the videos about the visitors experience in the museums</p>
4	<p>Style and Language SCORE: 4 (good) TEXT: The paper is well written and very easy to read.</p>	<p>The author(s) thank the anonymous reviewer for the encouraging comments</p>

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